

Appendix D

Supplementary information: Chapter 5

D.1 Liquid hydrogen vs conventional aircraft GWP model

We consider the case of a single flight from London Heathrow to New York JFK *via* an LH₂ vs a conventionally fuelled Boeing 787-9 aircraft. The fuel requirement was determined by integrating the power requirement over two key phases of flight: 1) the takeoff and climb to bring an aircraft from the ground up to its cruising altitude, and 2) the cruise to the end destination. The change in fuel burn during descent is neglected. For combustion-powered flight, the mass of the aircraft falls as fuel is consumed, hence the need to integrate the time-varying power to sustain lift over the course of the flight, yielding the Breguet range equations in **Eqs. D.1** and **D.2** for climb and cruise, respectively:

$$\frac{M_{\text{takeoff}}}{M_{\text{cruise}}} = \left(1 + \frac{g}{\left(\frac{L}{D}\right)_{cl} \eta_{TOT E}} R_{\text{climb}} \right)^{\left[\tan(\theta) \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)_{cl} + 1 \right]}, \quad (\text{D.1})$$

$$\frac{M_{\text{cruise}}}{M_{\text{landing}}} = \exp \left(\frac{g}{\left(\frac{L}{D}\right) \eta_{TOT E}} [R_{\text{journey}} - R_{\text{climb}}] \right), \quad (\text{D.2})$$

where

M_{takeoff} = total mass at takeoff (aircraft + passengers + cargo + fuel) [kg] ,

M_{cruise} = total mass at start of cruise [kg] ,

M_{landing} = total mass at landing [kg] ,

$\left(\frac{L}{D}\right)$ = lift-to-drag ratio during steady cruise flight ,

$\left(\frac{L}{D}\right)_{\text{cl}}$ = lift-to-drag ratio during climb flight ,

θ = climb angle ,

E = specific energy of fuel [kJ kg^{-1}] ,

η_{TOT} = overall efficiency ,

g = gravitational constant [m s^{-2}] ,

R_{climb} = distance travelled during climb [m] ,

R_{journey} = total journey distance [m] .

The climb distance, R_{climb} is estimated by considering the climb velocity, u_{cl} , (assumed constant throughout the climb), the climb angle, θ , and the cruising height H (altitude changes during the flight are neglected):

$$R_{\text{climb}} = \frac{H}{\tan(\theta)} \quad (\text{D.4})$$

Multiplying **Eqs. D.1** and **D.2** yields the ratio of the takeoff and landing masses, which may be expressed as:

$$\frac{M_{\text{takeoff}}}{M_{\text{landing}}} = \phi = \frac{Z + m_f}{Z + rm_f} , \quad (\text{D.5})$$

where m_f is the mass of fuel loaded, r is the reserve factor (*i.e.* the fraction of loaded fuel which is in reserve in case of journey deviation – assumed to be 10%), and Z is the zero-fuel weight (ZFW) of the aircraft given by:

$$Z = EW + \text{passenger capacity} \times p + \text{cargo capacity} \times c , \quad (\text{D.6})$$

where p is the mass of a passenger + baggage (taken as 100 kg), c is the average density of cargo (assumed 700 kg m^{-3}), and EW is the empty weight of the aircraft. Hence, the mass of

kerosene jet fuel required for a given journey is given by a simple rearrangement of **Eq. D.5**:

$$m_f = \frac{Z(\phi - 1)}{1 - r\phi}, \quad (\text{D.7})$$

where ϕ is the ratio of takeoff and landing masses as defined in **Eq. D.5**.

When using LH₂, however, the need for insulated tanks must be accounted for. Here, we consider exchanging a portion of the onboard cargo hold and cabin volume to make room for the tanks, thereby reducing the cargo and passenger capacity of the aircraft. In estimating the displaced volume of cargo and passengers by the liquid hydrogen, we consider directly the dead volume of the tanks themselves (arising from the walls and layers of insulation), quantified here using a volumetric efficiency, v . The mass of the onboard tanks is then given by considering the gravimetric efficiency, γ , of the fuel storage:

$$\text{mass of tanks} = m_f \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - 1 \right) \quad (\text{D.8})$$

The aircraft *EW* therefore changes owing to the added mass of the empty tanks, but this is offset by having fewer seats for passengers as described by:

$$EW = EW_{base} + m_f \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - 1 \right) - (\text{number of passengers removed} \times \text{mass of a seat}), \quad (\text{D.9})$$

where EW_{base} is the normal empty weight for the unmodified aircraft. The mass of a passenger seat, and associated auxiliary items on the aircraft, was estimated as 50 kg. Hence, the required mass of liquid hydrogen fuel is calculated by combining **Eqs. D.6, D.7 and D.9** and rearranging for the fuel mass, m_f .

Below, we summarise the key assumptions made in evaluating the fuel burn model for kerosene and liquid hydrogen fuels:

- The overall efficiency of propulsion, η_{TOT} , was taken as 40% for both kerosene and liquid hydrogen combustion.
- The aerodynamics of the aircraft, summarised by the L/D ratios, were taken as unaffected by the different fuels and loading of onboard tanks.
- The gravimetric and volumetric efficiencies for liquid hydrogen were taken as $\gamma = 70\%$ and $v = 60\%$, respectively [101].

D.1.1 Example Journey: London to New York

Taking a greater circle distance across the globe, the point-to-point flight distance, R_{journey} , between London Heathrow and New York JFK is 5,960 km. We consider flying the journey in a Boeing 787-9, for which data were primarily taken from, or estimated using, the manufacturer's data sheet [24]. Information regarding climbout and cruise speeds, as well as climb angle (θ) a cruising altitude (H) were taken from Eurocontrol [Eurocontrol]. Ordinarily, if using jet fuel, the maximum range of the B787-9 is around 14,000 km; for liquid hydrogen, it was necessary to remove 80% of the cargo capacity and 40% of the passengers to achieve an estimated range of 6,150 km, sufficient for the journey from London to New York. In **Tab. D.1** we show the subsequent effects on the aircraft empty weight, EW , and passenger capacity between the kerosene jet fuel and liquid hydrogen scenarios, alongside other salient data.

Table D.1 Summary of the key values used in estimating the fuel burn for kerosene and liquid hydrogen in a Boeing 787-9 aircraft.

Parameter	Value	
	Kerosene	LH ₂
L/D for cruise and descent	14.5	
L/D for takeoff and climbout	19.5	
Empty weight, EW [kg]	128,850	119,960
Zero fuel weight, Z [kg]	181,440	161,500
Passenger capacity	290	174
Cargo volume [m ³]	172	35
Climb angle, θ	5°	
Cruising altitude, H [ft]	40000	

Using the values summarised in **Tab. D.1**, the fuel burn was calculated for each fuel to yield the results summarised in **Tab. D.2**

Table D.2 Summary of the calculated fuel burn, normalised first per passenger and then by distance travelled.

Output	Value	
	Kerosene	LH ₂
Fuel required, m_f [kg]	43,140	11,780
Passengers carried, pax	290	174
Fuel per passenger [kg/pax]	148.8	67.7
Fuel per passenger per 100 km [kg/pax 100 km]	2.50	1.14

The GWP of an LH₂ vs a conventional (jet fuel) aircraft, was calculated per mission and per passenger using the key values summarised in Table D.2 and accounting for the GWP calculated for production of UK grid- and UK wind-based 50% and 85% LpH₂. The emissions of the LH₂ fuels include H₂ production, liquefaction with both perfect and imperfect OPC, transport (see **Section 5.2.1**), and boil-off venting (see **Figure 5.4** and **Figure 5.6**). We consider the use of the fuel in the LH₂ aircraft after one day (**Figure 5.7**), two days (**Figure 5.8**), and seven days (**Figure 5.9**) post-liquefaction.

D.2 Tabulated GWP results

Table D.3 GWP results for 25-99.6% LpH₂ production (gCO_{2,eq}/MJ_{LH₂}) accounting for hydrogen production *via* water electrolysis, liquefaction, transportation, boil-off leakage (up to 15%), replenishment of the boil-off with LH₂ of the same p-H₂% for both the grid-based and wind-based processes.

LH ₂ product quality	Time after liquefaction (days)	Grid-based process	Wind-based process	LH ₂ product quality	Time after liquefaction (days)	GWP of grid-based process	GWP of wind-based process
25%	0	239.8	4.3	83%	0.0	241.8	4.4
	1	283.8	6.8		1.0	244.6	4.6
	2	309.7	8.2		2.0	247.3	4.7
	3	326.7	9.2		3.0	249.6	4.8
	4	338.5	9.9		4.0	251.7	5.0
	5	347.3	10.4		5.0	253.7	5.1
	6	354.0	10.8		6.0	255.5	5.2
	7	359.4	11.1		7.0	257.1	5.3
	15	380.0	12.3		15.0	266.7	5.8
	30	391.3	12.9		30.0	275.9	6.3
	40	394.3	13.1		40.0	279.4	6.5
	60	397.5	13.3		60.0	283.7	6.8
	90	399.7	13.4		90.0	287.2	7.0
	100	400.1	13.4		100.0	287.9	7.0
	150	401.5	13.5		150.0	290.4	7.2
	200	402.1	13.5		200.0	291.7	7.2
	250	402.5	13.5		250.0	292.5	7.3
300	402.8	13.6	300.0	293.1	7.3		
365	403.1	13.6	365.0	293.6	7.3		
50%	0	240.5	4.3	95%	0.0	242.6	4.4
	1	262.5	5.6		1.0	243.0	4.5
	2	278.1	6.4		2.0	243.3	4.5
	3	289.8	7.1		3.0	243.7	4.5
	4	298.8	7.6		4.0	244.0	4.5
	5	306.0	8.0		5.0	244.3	4.5
	6	311.9	8.4		6.0	244.7	4.6
	7	316.8	8.7		7.0	245.0	4.6
	15	337.9	9.9		15.0	247.1	4.7
	30	351.2	10.6		30.0	250.0	4.9
	40	355.1	10.8		40.0	251.4	4.9
	60	359.3	11.1		60.0	253.5	5.1
	90	362.2	11.2		90.0	255.5	5.2
	100	362.8	11.3		100.0	256.0	5.2
	150	364.7	11.4		150.0	257.8	5.3
	200	365.6	11.4		200.0	258.9	5.4
	250	366.2	11.5		250.0	259.7	5.4
300	366.6	11.5	300.0	260.2	5.4		
365	366.9	11.5	365.0	260.7	5.5		
69%	0	241.2	4.3	99.6%	0.0	243.1	4.5
	1	250.8	4.9		1.0	243.1	4.5
	2	258.7	5.3		2.0	243.1	4.5
	3	265.2	5.7		3.0	243.1	4.5
	4	270.7	6.0		4.0	243.1	4.5
	5	275.4	6.3		5.0	243.1	4.5
	6	279.4	6.5		6.0	243.1	4.5
	7	282.9	6.7		7.0	243.1	4.5
	15	300.2	7.7		15.0	243.1	4.5
	30	313.2	8.5		30.0	243.1	4.5
	40	317.4	8.7		40.0	243.1	4.5
	60	322.1	9.0		60.0	243.2	4.5
	90	325.5	9.2		90.0	243.2	4.5
	100	326.2	9.2		100.0	243.3	4.5
	150	328.5	9.3		150.0	243.3	4.5
	200	329.7	9.4		200.0	243.4	4.5
	250	330.4	9.4		250.0	243.5	4.5
300	330.9	9.5	300.0	243.5	4.5		
365	331.3	9.5	365.0	243.6	4.5		